

FROM PLAYGROUND TO PRECOCIOUS PUBERTY: HOW COVID-19 TURNED PUBERTY INTO A PANDEMIC, A MULTI-COUNTRY STUDY.

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ABSTRACT

Puberty is a critical phase in human development, and its timing can be influenced by various factors. This meta-analysis aimed to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on precocious puberty covers three studies from Italy, Brazil, and China. A statistically significant correlation was observed between the pandemic and a rise in the incidence of precocious puberty.

The COVID-19 pandemic and associated stress, lifestyle changes, and altered socioeconomic conditions may have contributed to the observed increase in precocious puberty. Further research is needed to better understand the mechanisms underlying these associations and to develop strategies for mitigating the impact on children's health and well-being.

Keywords: Covid-19, precocious puberty, lifestyle changes, obesity, menarche, screen time.

1. Introduction:

Puberty represents the dynamic phase when an individual transitions from childhood to adulthood, acquiring full reproductive capacity. In girls, puberty typically begins with the development of breasts (thelarche) and is later followed by the onset of the first menstrual period (menarche), occurring approximately three years later. The timing of puberty varies considerably among individuals, ranging from 8 to 13 years of age in girls and 9 to 14 years in boys.

During normal puberty, the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis is activated, leading to the development of secondary sexual characteristics. Puberty begins with the release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) in a pulsatile pattern, mainly during sleep. This secretion stimulates the release of both follicle-stimulating hormone FSH and luteinizing hormone LH from the pituitary gland. In females, FSH promotes the maturation of ovarian follicles and the production of estrogen, while LH stimulates the production of androgens which triggers ovulation. In males, FSH affects spermatogenesis while LH helps with testosterone production.

a shift towards an earlier puberty onset has been observed for the last few decades. In 1973, the medium menarche age was 12.8 years in females [1] while in 2016/2017 it was 11.1 years [2]. this change was correlated with genetic factors, environmental changes, diet, body weight and endocrine disruptors. However the incidence of early puberty, also called precocious puberty has increased worldwide during the covid-19 pandemic.

Precocious puberty is a medical condition in which a child's body begins to develop and mature earlier than usual. This can include the development of breasts, pubic hair, and menstruation in girls, and the growth of facial and body hair, deepening of the voice, and enlargement of the testicles in boys.

Precocious puberty can be classified into two categories: central (true) precocious puberty and peripheral (incomplete) precocious puberty. Central precocious puberty (CPP) is characterized by its dependence

on gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and is frequently of idiopathic origin, accounting for approximately 75% of cases. Peripheral precocious puberty (PPP); also known as pseudo puberty is GnRH-independent and is caused by exogenous sex steroids secretion.

At the end of 2019, a novel coronavirus known as SARS-CoV-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2) was identified as the underlying cause of an outbreak of atypical pneumonia in China. This newly emerged disease, referred to as Covid-19, rapidly spread across the globe, ultimately resulting in a widespread pandemic.

In March of 2020, hospitals were completely saturated with maximum occupancy of beds in the intensive care units. In an attempt to limit the spread of Covid-19; global lockdown and strict quarantine measures were applied. As schools shifted to e-learning, and different job positions adapted to remote work regime using different digital platforms, lifestyle changes had to be applied.

During the lockdown and after the end of the strict quarantine measures, an increase in the outpatient consultations for suspected precocious puberty was recorded worldwide. In Italy consultation increased by 122% while Brazil reported 50%, china reported an increase from 0.4% in 2018 to 6.23% in 2020.

It was noted through all 3 studies that time spent on electronic devices increased during lockdown, while daily physical activity decreased. Eating habits changed and stress related symptoms were observed in children and adolescents throughout the pandemic.

2. Methods:

Subjects:

the Italian study covered 490 subjects above the age of 3 years, divided into 2019 and 2020 groups, and four subgroups based on their diagnosis including: transient thelarche (TT), non-progressive precocious puberty (NPP), central precocious puberty (CPP), and early puberty (EP) from March- September 2019 compared to March- September 2020.

The Brazilian study had the smaller sample size with 55 subjects divided into two groups; a convenience sample including 22 girls diagnosed with precocious puberty during Covid from July 2020 to June 2021 and a control group of 33 girls diagnosed with precocious puberty prior to covid from March 2019 to February 2020.

The Chinese study covered 240 subjects between the age of 5-9 years and were divided into two groups; a convenience group including 58 girls diagnosed with central precocious puberty, and 58 girls diagnosed with transient thelarche. And a control group including 124 healthy age matched girls. This investigation was between February and May 2020.

Exclusion / inclusion:

All three studies excluded boys as females are 5 times affected than males for the idiopathic variant of precocious puberty. The Italian study included 10 boys who were later excluded because there was no difference between the results of 2020 and 2019 with 10 vs 12 cases respectively.

Studies also excluded precocious puberty associated with hypothalamic-pituitary malformations, congenital adrenal hyperplasia, neurological and genetic diseases, psychomotor retardation and endocrine diseases that require hormonal treatment or caused by exogenous factors, different intracranial lesions and Silver Russell Syndrome.

Data collection:

Physical examination:

All three studies measured the pubertal age according to Marshall & Tanner's genital stage. Height, weight and BMI of the subjects was expressed as standard deviation score SDS according to World Health Organization (WHO) Graphs.

The Chinese paper included abdominal and hip circumference, a physical examination of the cardiopulmonary system, the liver and the spleen.

Laboratory measures:

The Italian study measured Estradiol, leuteinizing hormone (LH), follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and testosterone levels. And Gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) stimulation test was performed.

The Brazilian study measured Estradiol, LH, and FSH.

While the Chinese study measured melatonin and serotonin levels, both leptin and kisspeptin levels, LH, FSH, E2 and vitamin D levels. Tests on the cardiovascular system, liver and kidney function, thyroid function and Insulin-like growth factor-1 were performed.

Bone age assessment:

All three studies assessed the bone age through the Greulich and Pyle method.

The Chinese study included abdominal and hip circumference.

Imaging:

A pelvic ultrasound was performed on both the Italian and Brazilian studies and assessed the maturity of the reproductive system. The Italian paper focused on uterine longitudinal diameter (mm) and endometrium pattern, while the Brazil's paper focused on the ovarian volume (ml).

While the Chinese study performed a gonadal color doppler ultrasound and pituitary magnetic resonance imaging.

Questionnaire:

The Italian lifestyle questionnaire included physical activity, different eating habits, screen time and electronic use, and pandemic related stress.

The Brazilian questionnaire covered physical activity, eating habits and electronic use.

The Chinese study covered a wider range of potential factors including but not limited to: sex, age, place of residence, date of diagnosis. Parental information including career, educational background, and mother's menstrual age, time spent with parents Physical activity, eating habits, electronic use, sleeping schedule, second hand smoke, exposure to hazardous substances, the use of adult cosmetics, use of plastic products, etc...

3. Results:

3.1 the Italian study results after analyzing 152 subjects between March - September 2019 compared to 338 subjects in 2020 of the same period showed a clean increase of +122%

This increase was strongly noted in girls compared to boys especially during the second half of the period, whereas the boys, showed no difference.

The family history was positive for early puberty in 30% of the total female subjects with no difference between 2019 and 2020.

Both the 2019 and 2020 subgroups were found to have a postnatal weight gained.

As for the percentage of girls diagnosed in 2020 and 2019 respectively with Central precocious puberty is 41% vs 26%. Early puberty at 10% vs 17%. Transient thelarche with no difference. Non progressive puberty with no difference.

Life style questionnaire revealed an increase in the use of electronic devices due to e-learning during quarantine while still maintaining the same 5-10h/week on online leisure activities. A noticeable decrease in physical activity in the majority of subjects was observed, from (1-2h/week) in 2019 vs (never to 1-2 h/week) in 2020 vs leading a sedentary lifestyle. Hello

47% of the subjects reported an increase in hunger and craving of sweets. While 59% of the subjects reported pandemic related stress.

Figure 1: CPP physical activity (Italy)

Figure 2: Weekly use of electronic devices in 2020 (Italy)

Figure 3: Weekly use of electronic devices in 2020 (Italy)

3.2. the Brazilian study analyzed 55 girls, divided into two groups, 22 girls diagnosed with precocious puberty during Covid-19 from July 2020 to June 2021, and 33 girls diagnosed prior to Covid from March 2019 to February 2020.

The clinical, laboratory and radiological data concluded that the subjects who developed PP during the pandemic were more advanced in age (7.15 vs 6.74 years; $p = 0.10$). However, according to the parents' perception of the breast to diagnosis was much lower (6.65 vs 12.15 month; $p + 0.02$). The girls were on average taller with a mean Z-score for height of (0.76 vs 0.22), and the weight was higher as obesity was more prevalent in the group that developed PP during the pandemic.

The bone age and chronological age were similar between the two groups. And the laboratory results did not indicate any difference. However, the pelvic ultrasound showed reduced pubertal ovary in girls diagnosed with PP during covid compared to the girls who were diagnosed prior to covid, and these results match with the ones of an Italian study done in 2019 on 39 female subjects diagnosed with CPP as shown in the ultrasound in figure 4. [3]

The lifestyle questionnaire revealed increased exposure to electronic devices due to e-learning., major dietary changes such as a higher consumption of carbohydrates and sugary drinks, and lower physical activity as a result of quarantine which eventually led to a higher BMI.

Figure 4: Ovarian ultrasound of a girl diagnosed with precocious puberty during the COVID-19 pandemic showing a reduced pubertal ovary. The patient started puberty at 7 years and 3 months (May 2020); August 2020: height 1.67 SDS, weight 1.53 SDS, BMI 1.1 SDS, Tanner stage 3.

3.3 the Chinese study stated that the number of female new onset of precocious puberty out-patient data collected from 22 medical institutes shows in increase from 4281 girls in February - may 2020 (5.01 times more) compared to 1346 girls in 2019 (3.14 time more) and 855 girls in 2018.

From February to May 2020, there were 2,141 consultations, which is 20.01 times higher than the number of consultations in the same period in 2018 (107 visits). It is also 6.21 times higher than the number of consultations in the same period in 2019 (345 visits).

This increase represents a significant growth from 0.41% in 2018 to 9.88% in 2022. These results were constant throughout all multi-center study.

Analysis of the risk factors shows that girls who received a diagnosis of central precocious puberty (CPP) and PT were significantly taller and overweight in comparison to the group of individuals serving as controls.

The convenience group was exposed to many other risk factors including less physical activity, prolonged use of electronic devices, frequent use of night

light, a notable deficiency of vitamin D, younger age of mother's menarche, the use of adult cosmetics, residence in rural settings, expose to second hand smoke etc.

Figure 5: CPP vs PT physical activity (china)

Figure 6: CPP italy vs CPP china physical activity.

The related hormone measurements showed a notable difference in serotonin, melatonin, leptin, and kisspeptin levels across all the three groups.

The CPP group had higher LH, FSH, E2 and leptin levels. Whereas the TT group had a higher MT, FSH, E2 and leptin levels.

Serotonin was higher in the control group, with CPP and TT groups being the same.

Kisspeptin was noticeably higher in CPP and TT groups than the control group in which CPP and TT groups being the same.

Melatonin levels were higher in PT groups than the control group. However, there were no significant

differences observed in these levels between the CPP and TT groups, as well as between the CPP and control groups.

The data obtained from the questionnaire revealed several significant factors, including prolonged usage of electronic devices, reduced physical activity, unhealthy eating habits characterized by the consumption of processed and fried foods, elevated BMI, deficiency in vitamin D, and extensive exposure to secondhand smoke, the use of adult cosmetics, and living in rural areas.

Table 1

Anthropometric characteristics of patients with precocious puberty during the covid-19

	Italy	Brazil	China SDS	China
CA	7.39 ± 0.84	7.70 ± 0.62	7.31 ± 1.00	7.31 ± 1.00
BA	8.87 ± 1.22	9.55 ± 1.34	8.91 ± 1.32	8.91 ± 1.32
Height SDS	0.82 ± 1.01	0.76 ± 1.19	1.55 ± 2.3	132.76 ± 7.01
Weight SDS	0.52 ± 1.01	1.08 ± 1.29	1.66 ± 1.15	32.93 ± 6.57
BMI SDS	0.24 ± 1.54	0.96 ± 1.34	1.32 ± 0.16	18.02 ± 2.36
Overweight	-	22.73%	22.41%	22.41%
Obesity	-	36.36%	22.41%	22.41%

CPP, central precocious puberty; CA, chronological age; BA, bone age; BMI, body mass index. Parameters are expressed as standard deviation score (SDS). mean ±.

Table 2

Laboratory parameters in patients with precocious puberty during the covid-19 pandemic.

	Italy	Brazil	China
LH (IU / L)	1.21 ± 1.72	1.28 ± 2.17	1.96 ± 2.50
FSH (IU / L)	3.95 ± 2.12	4.33 ± 3.05	3.48 ± 1.91
Estradiol (pg /ml)	12.13 ± 20.17	25.61 ± 15.97	
Ovarian volume (ml)	3.32 ± 0.42 cm ³	1.88 ± 0.95	

4. Discussion:

All three studies show an increase in reported precocious puberty cases during the pandemic.

The Italian paper is the only one not to report a weight gain in its subjects, that could be due to many factors; including the Mediterranean diet that's rich in antioxidants or the active lifestyle. Some studies show that even when Italian children gain weight, the obesity is uncomplicated and rarely does it develop to something more serious with long term conditions [4].

The Covid-19 pandemic was a stressful period of time. schools switched to an online format and quarantine was implemented, preventing kids from socializing and being around friends. Masks were implemented and the news talked about Covid deaths and complications 24/7, millions of people lost their jobs, while kids were isolated home. The combination of inevitable exposure to the socioeconomic effect of covid with complete home isolation for months can have a psycho-emotional effect on children. In china, 22.6% of primary school children reported depressive symptoms while 18.9% reported stress and anxiety [5].

Dietary changes were observed around the world with people reporting noticeable weight gain during the initial three-month period of quarantine. However this behavioral change in eating habits is unique to Covid quarantine. Quarantine allowed people to stay more at home, surrounded by their families which gives them more time to cook and prepare healthy meals. And grocery shopping became easier because stores don't struggle with rush-hour anymore and home delivery is readily available. Even with all these factors that are supposed to push for a healthier eating; snacks, sugary drinks and carbohydrates were the most consumed. This binge eating behavior can be traced back to the psycho-emotional state of the children. A study done in 2014 showed that people in a good mood tend to favor healthier food with a higher level of benefits and smaller portions, while subjects with neutral to negative moods chose unhealthy food and larger portions to consume [6]. Menarche is associated with height rather than age, and needs at least 22% body fat to be triggered, which is among the contributing factors why it occurs earlier in overweight girls [7].

An average 8 year old nowadays spends 6 hours in front of a screen, however this activity doubled during quarantine due to e-learning, and communicating with friends through different social media platforms, however, the average personal leisure time did not go down, resulting in kids spending 27% more time on electronic devices everyday [8].

The OSF healthcare recommends a maximum of 2 hours screen time per day for individuals aged 5 to 17 [9]. Children spending long hours in front of electronic devices exposes them to electromagnetic radiation.

Many studies show the negative effect of EMF on the human body, especially children. EMF are known to have a negative effect on the fetal development, neurological development, the reproduction system in both females and males, endocrine disturbances.

In 1950s, Soviet medical researchers identified "radiofrequency radiation sickness", and its symptoms

observed encompassed headaches, fatigue, sleep disturbances, and other related effects that are typically reversible during the early stages. The study further determined that in the long term, these symptoms can potentially lead to the development of tumors, reproductive and cardiovascular abnormalities, as well as contribute to depression, irritability, and memory impairment. [10]

The reproductive system is highly susceptible to the effects and influences observed in various physiological and environmental factors. An experiment done on cows which were exposed to 60Hz EMF for 4 weeks (16 hours per day), showed an alteration in circulating melatonin and prolactin levels, as well as the estrous cycle [11] while another study showed that EMF exposure in female rats lead to a decrease in the number of their follicles. the follicles become defected after exposure but keep growing, resulting in later complications [12][13]. The effect of EMF on children is dependent on: frequency, duration and strength of the radiation.[13] but nonetheless, it can have a permanent effect on the body especially the reproductive system.

Not only does the long use of electronics exposes the children to EMF, the blue light from the screen has very serious effects on the body. Melatonin is hormone that's produced by the pineal gland, it has an antioxidant effect that lowers DNA damage. [10]. Inadequate sleep quality and heightened fatigue have been associated with decreased levels of nocturnal melatonin and increased levels of nocturnal norepinephrine [10]. melatonin regulates the pulse of LHRH in the hypothalamus, influencing gonadotropin FSH and LH. When melatonin is decreased, it alters The synthesis of sex hormones, resulting in changes in the reproductive cycle such as infertility [13]. Many studies have shown a direct relation between poor sleeping habits and weight gain, with obesity being more common in kids with irregular sleeping schedules [14]

Obesity in children is more dangerous than adults, an experiment done in 2021, showed that mice who had been subjected to a diet rich in fat at a young age developed precocious puberty and indulged in risky behaviors, the mice were later exposed to a healthier diet in adulthood and lost weight, however, the effect of PP had an irreversible neural damage like memory impairment and high anxiety [15], some other studies show that it's harder for obese kids to lose weight as adults due to their neurological and metabolic permanent changes that occurred during puberty. [14]

Genetics and maternal lifestyle play a big factor in the development of precocious puberty. Early menarche may be trans-generation, some studies have found that the mother of the child and the mother of the father's monarch age may predict the age of the child's first menstrual cycle [16]. An association was made between the onset of menarche and the risk of diabetes in adults, where it was revealed that a lower age of menarche in girls is associated with an increased likelihood of developing diabetes mellitus later in life due to increased adiposity [17] while girls with early menarche age tend to have rapid weight gain and growth during infancy, which leads to taller childhood status and earlier maturation, therefore shorter adult stature, which

explains the 95 percentile height in the girls compared to their peers. This growth pattern was shown to be increase adult obesity risks [16]

While a study done on treated and untreated women with idiopathic precocious puberty, found that the untreated women suffer long term outcomes, like neurological and endocrine dysfunction, hyperandrogenism, and higher infertility problems [18] while 15% of women who suffered ICPP had oligomenorrhea, 28% had clinical hyperandrogenism, 48% biochemical hyperandrogenism, and 37% PCOM. The study also found that patients with ICPP are prone to develop PCOS at least 3 years after menarche (18 years old / +/- 3 years). A total of 32% of the patients had PCOS according to the Rotterdam definition and 30% had PCOS according to the Androgen Excess Society. [19]

Conclusion:

Our findings suggest a significant correlation between the incidence of precocious puberty cases during the COVID pandemic and an unhealthy lifestyle. Factors such as an imbalanced diet, limited physical activity, excessive screen time, genetic predisposition, and exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals have been shown to negatively impact the onset of precocious puberty. Therefore, we recommend the implementation of a healthy, well-rounded lifestyle, including a balanced diet rich in fruits and vegetables, regular exercise and outdoor activity, parental supervision of screen time, and increased attention to the child's mental and physical health, to facilitate early detection and diagnosis.

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References marked with an asterisk indicate studies included in the meta-analysis.

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